

**POLICY
PRACTICE**

**SOCIAL
WORKERS
FOR
SOCIAL
JUSTICE**

ORIGINAL VERSION

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International Policy Practice Questionnaire

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INTRODUCTION PAGE AND CONSENT

Dear colleague,

Welcome to this online survey that focuses on your social work education, occupational background, and current professional activity, both in terms of helping individuals and working towards social change. The study was approved by the BGU's ethics committee (approval #OG20022023) and reviewed by the data protection representatives of HS Neubrandenburg and OST.

There are no "right" or "wrong" answers; your perspective is important. Your participation in the survey will take about 20 minutes and is completely voluntary. If you do participate in the survey, you can skip any question. You can also leave the survey at any time without penalty. Throughout the survey, we don't ask for personal information, such as your name or address, and we don't store your IP address. Therefore, your participation is completely anonymous, and there is no way for us to identify you as a participant.

There are no risks or direct benefits to you for participating in this survey. However, the information that you provide will help to inform recommendations for improvements in the field of social work. If you have any questions about this study, please contact us.

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this study. Have fun filling out the survey! We wish you all the best,

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By answering "yes" to the following question, you are agreeing to be part of this study.

- Yes, I have read and understood the above information and I wish to participate in this study.
- No, I do not want to participate in this study.

1 OCCUPATIONAL BACKGROUND

This first section focuses on your occupational background and serves to filter out participants who do not match the target group of this study.

1.1 Occupation 1

Which category best describes your current occupation? I am...

- a social worker (including social work academics, politicians, administrators, and managers)
- a social work student without professional social work experience
- a social work student with professional social work experience
- a retired social worker
- a social worker but currently unemployed
- none of the above

[Source: developed for this study]

1.2 Occupation 2. Filter. Show if 1.1 = (2) OR (6)

Thank you for your interest in this research. This study's population is active social workers. As you are not (yet) working professionally in the field of social work, you do not match the target group of this study. If you accidentally chose these categories, you can click [here](#) and choose another option. Otherwise, click "submit."

[Source: developed for this study]

1.3 Occupation 3. Filter. Show if 1.1 = (3)

At what level are you studying?

- Bachelor of Social Work
- Master of Social Work
- PhD/DSW

[Source: developed for this study]

1.4 Occupation 4. Filter. Show if 1.1 = (3)

Are you currently working in the field of social work besides your studies?

- Yes
- No

[Source: developed for this study]

2 EMPLOYMENT SITUATION

Filter: This section will only be displayed to participants who are currently working in the field of social work (see Section 1).

The following questions refer to your job in your principal working place as a social worker.

2.1 Years in Total

How many years in total have you worked as a social worker?

- Open Number Field

[Source: developed for this study]

2.2 Years in Current Organization

How many years have you worked in your current organization?
(Example: 20 percent = one work day per week)

- Open Number Field

[Source: developed for this study]

2.3 Percent

What percent of time do you work in your primary working place?
(Example: 20 percent = 1 day per week)

- 0-10
- 11-20
- 21-30
- 31-40
- 41-50
- 51-60
- 61-70
- 71-80
- 81-90
- 91-100

[Source: developed for this study]

2.4 Location

In which state is your primary working place located?

- Dropdown Menu with a list of all states

[Source: developed for this study]

2.5 Tenure

Do you have permanent employment/tenure?

- Yes

- No

[Source: developed for this study]

2.6 Position

Which of the following best describes your current position within the organization for which you work?

- Intern
- Frontline worker (I work directly with the people we serve)
- Program director / team leader / mid-level manager
- Upper-level manager
- Executive director
- Other: [add open textfield here]

[Source: developed for this study]

2.7 Area of Practice 1

Please identify your primary area of practice. [THIS LIST MUST BE ADAPTED TO THE RESPECTIVE CONTEXT OF THE COUNTRY. BELOW IS THE LIST FOR THE SWISS SURVEY]

- Altersarbeit
- Arbeits-/Berufsintegration
- Behindertenbereich
- Betriebliche Sozialarbeit
- Erziehungs-/Familienberatung
- Finanz-/Schuldenberatung
- Flucht/Migration
- Forschung/Lehre
- Gemeinwesenarbeit/Sozialraumarbeit
- Gesundheitswesen
- Jugendarbeit
- Kindergarten/Kita/Krippe
- Kindes-/Erwachsenenschutz
- Obdach/Wohnintegration
- Opferhilfe
- Schule
- Sozialhilfe
- Stationäre Kinder- und Jugendhilfe
- Straf-/Massnahmenvollzug
- Suchtberatung/-therapie
- Verbandsarbeit
- Anderes

[Source: developed for this study]

2.8 Area of Practice 2

Please indicate your exact job position within the area of practice you selected above. (e.g., probation officer if you selected correction/parole)

- Open Text Field

[Source: developed for this study]

3 PSYCHOLOGICAL INVOLVEMENT IN POLITICS

This section focuses on political attitudes, political interest, and political efficacy.

3.1 Political Interest

How interested would you say you are in politics?

- Very interested
- Quite interested
- Hardly interested
- Not at all interested

[Source: ESS, 2020, question B1]

3.2 External Political Efficacy 1

How much would you say the political system in [country] allows people like you to have a say in what the government does?

- Not at all
- Very little
- Some
- A lot
- A great deal

[Source: ESS, 2020, question B2]

3.3 External Political Efficacy 2

And how much would you say that the political system in [country] allows people like you to have an influence on politics?

- Not at all
- Very little
- Some
- A lot
- A great deal

[Source: ESS, 2020, question B4]

3.4 Internal Political Efficacy 1

How able do you think you are to take an active role in a group involved with political issues?

- Not at all able
- A little able
- Quite able
- Very able
- Completely able

[Source: ESS, 2020, question B3]

3.5 Internal Political Efficacy 2

And how confident are you in your own ability to participate in politics?

- Not at all confident
- A little confident
- Quite confident
- Very confident
- Completely confident

[Source: ESS, 2020, question B5]

3.6 Political Ideology

In politics people sometimes talk of “left” and “right”. Where would you place yourself on this scale, where 0 means the left and 10 means the right?

- 0 = the left
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10 = the right

[Source: ESS, 2020, question B26]

3.7 Partisanship 1

Is there a particular political party you feel closer to than all the other parties?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

[Source: ESS, 2020, question B23]

3.8 Partisanship 2. Filter. Show if Partisanship 1 = “yes”

Which political party do you feel closer to than all the other parties?

- List of all parties in the respective country

[Source: ESS, 2020, question B24]

4 RECRUITMENT NETWORKS

In this section, we ask about your affiliation with, and your activity level in, different political networks and groups.

4.1 Level of Engagement in Recruitment Networks

Please rate how active you are in the following networks and groups:

		(0) Not a member, (1) Passive, (2) Rather passive, (3) Rather active, (4) Active				
1	Student organizations	0	1	2	3	4
2	Social and/or political movements (e.g., Black Lives Matter, Fridays for Future)	0	1	2	3	4
3	Advocacy/non-governmental organizations (e.g., Amnesty International)	0	1	2	3	4
4	Trade unions	0	1	2	3	4
5	Political parties	0	1	2	3	4
6	Professional association of social workers (AvenirSocial, DBSH, NASW etc.)	0	1	2	3	4
7	Scientific associations of social workers	0	1	2	3	4
8	Social work activism groups	0	1	2	3	4
9	Other social work organizations/groups (e.g., AGJ, School Social Work Association)	0	1	2	3	4

[Source: based on Verba, et al., 1995; Schlozman et al., 2018 and modified by Kindler, 2021; Kindler & Ostrander, 2022; Weiss-Gal & Gal, 2020]

5 LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT IN POLICY PRACTICE

The next questions focus on your activities to influence policies as part of your job as a social worker (policy practice).

5.1 Level of Engagement in Policy Practice

We are interested in your activities to influence policies at the local, state, national, and/or international levels, as well as policies within the organization in which you work(ed). During your whole career as a social worker, to what extent have you taken part in the following activities to influence policies?

		(0) Never, (1) Rarely, (2) Sometimes, (3) Often, (4) Very often				
1	Working to improve social workers' working conditions	0	1	2	3	4
2	Communicating with a policymaker*	0	1	2	3	4
3	Inviting a policymaker* to visit your organization or the community/neighborhood in which you work	0	1	2	3	4
4	Communicating with another organization	0	1	2	3	4
5	Communicating with an association or union	0	1	2	3	4
6	Communicating with celebrities or influencers	0	1	2	3	4
7	Using social media	0	1	2	3	4
8	Communicating with the mass media (e.g., TV, radio, newspapers)	0	1	2	3	4
9	Collecting data, conducting a study, or using existing data	0	1	2	3	4
10	Collecting views and feedback from service users	0	1	2	3	4
11	Helping service users to influence policy	0	1	2	3	4
12	Attending a government/parliamentary committee at the local, state and/or national level	0	1	2	3	4
13	Taking part in an organized appeal to a court	0	1	2	3	4
14	Taking part in a civic action or protest activity (e.g., a petition, protest march, or rally)	0	1	2	3	4
15	Participating in a group (e.g., committee, planning body, etc.), coalition, or roundtable	0	1	2	3	4
16	Organizing an official meeting, seminar, or conference	0	1	2	3	4
17	Preparing a policy brief	0	1	2	3	4

*Note that policymakers are people that have the power to influence and/or decide policies. These can be managers, supervisors, or heads of your organization, as well as politicians and officials at all levels outside of the organization, or their assistants/advisors.

[Source: modified scale originally developed by Weiss-Gal et al., 2020]

5.2 Level of Engagement in Policy Practice at the Organizational, Local, State, National, and International Levels

Throughout your career as a social worker, to what extent have you taken part in activities to influence policies on the...

		(0) Never, (1) Rarely, (2) Sometimes, (3) Often, (4) Very often				
1	organizational level?	0	1	2	3	4
2	local level?	0	1	2	3	4
3	state level?	0	1	2	3	4
4	national level?	0	1	2	3	4
5	international level?	0	1	2	3	4

[Source: Tayri-Schwartz, 2015]

5.3 Open Text Field on the Level of Policy Practice Engagement

What would you like to add regarding your engagement in policy practice? Policy practice is defined as influencing policies as part of your job as social worker.

- Open Text Field

[Source: developed for this study]

6 ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT OF POLICY PRACTICE

6.1 Organizational Support of Policy Practice

The following statements refer to all social welfare service organizations in which you have worked during your career as a social worker. Please rate the extent to which you agree or disagree with each statement.

At the social welfare service organizations at which you have worked during your career:

		1=strongly disagree 5=strongly agree				
1	Agency leadership encouraged social workers to participate in activities aimed at influencing policies.	1	2	3	4	5
2	Social workers involved in activities aimed at influencing policies were viewed positively.	1	2	3	4	5
3	Information about the methods to contact policymakers was readily available in the organization.	1	2	3	4	5
4	There were specific discussions and meetings about policy issues.	1	2	3	4	5
5	Being involved in influencing policies helped workers' careers and promotion prospects.	1	2	3	4	5
6	Being involved in influencing policies hurt workers' careers and promotion prospects.	1	2	3	4	5
7	Social workers were offered in-house training on the ways they can influence policy.	1	2	3	4	5
8	Social workers were sent to seminars or conferences about policy issues.	1	2	3	4	5
9	Social workers who had been involved in influencing policies received recognition.	1	2	3	4	5
10	Influencing policies was part of social workers' job descriptions.	1	2	3	4	5

[Source: Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2017; Tayri-Schwartz, 2015]

7 BIG FIVE INVENTORY-2 (BFI-2-XS)

This section focuses on personality traits.

7.1 Big Five Inventory-2-XS

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements on your personality? I am someone who...

		1 = disagree strongly, 5 = agree strongly				
1	tends to be quiet.	1	2	3	4	5
2	is compassionate, has a soft heart.	1	2	3	4	5
3	tends to be disorganized.	1	2	3	4	5
4	worries a lot.	1	2	3	4	5
5	is fascinated by art, music, or literature.	1	2	3	4	5
6	is dominant, acts as a leader.	1	2	3	4	5
7	is sometimes rude to others.	1	2	3	4	5
8	has difficulty getting started on tasks.	1	2	3	4	5
9	tends to feel depressed, blue.	1	2	3	4	5
10	has little interest in abstract ideas.	1	2	3	4	5
11	is full of energy.	1	2	3	4	5
12	assumes the best about people.	1	2	3	4	5
13	is reliable, can always be counted on.	1	2	3	4	5
14	is emotionally stable, not easily upset.	1	2	3	4	5
15	is original, comes up with new ideas.	1	2	3	4	5

[Source: Soto & John, 2017a, 2017b]

8 POLICY PRACTICE EDUCATION

In this section, we ask about your social work education. For each question, please circle the answer that fits best.

8.1 Theoretical Foundations of Policy Practice

During your studies, how much did you learn about...

		1=not at all 5=very much				
1	the IFSW's and the IASSW's global definition of social work?	1	2	3	4	5
2	the ethical principles of social work?	1	2	3	4	5
3	social work as a micro, mezzo, and macro practice?	1	2	3	4	5
4	the connection between social work and social policies?	1	2	3	4	5
5	policy processes?	1	2	3	4	5
6	structural causes of social problems?	1	2	3	4	5
7	critical/radical social work?	1	2	3	4	5
8	theories of social justice?	1	2	3	4	5
9	different forms of discrimination (such as antisemitism, racism, sexism, ableism, and classism)?	1	2	3	4	5
10	social/political movements?	1	2	3	4	5

[Source: Burzlaff, 2020, 2021, 2022; Schwartz-Tayri, 2021]

8.2 Policy Practice in Practice

During your studies, how much did you...

		1=not at all 5=very much				
1	learn about social work methods of macro practice?	1	2	3	4	5
2	learn about the concept of policy practice?	1	2	3	4	5
3	learn about how to be engaged in policy practice?	1	2	3	4	5
4	simulate influencing policy?	1	2	3	4	5
5	participate in activities aimed at actually influencing policy?	1	2	3	4	5

[Source: Burzlaff, 2020, 2021, 2022; Schwartz-Tayri, 2021]

8.3 Open Text Field on Policy Practice Education

What would you like to add regarding policy related education?

- Open Text Field

[Source: developed for this study]

9 POLICY PRACTICE SKILLS

9.1 Policy Practice Skills

Generally speaking, do you think you have the proper skills to perform the following actions in order to influence policy? For each question, please circle the answer that fits you best.

		1=not at all skilled 5=highly skilled				
Political skills						
1	Organize protest activities (e.g., rallies, petitions)	1	2	3	4	5
2	Find resources to fund advocacy projects	1	2	3	4	5
3	Activate the public to participate in the policy-making process	1	2	3	4	5
4	Use traditional media (e.g., newspapers, TV)	1	2	3	4	5
5	Use social media	1	2	3	4	5
6	Initiate litigation	1	2	3	4	5

Analytical skills						
7	Develop a paper on a social or policy issue	1	2	3	4	5
8	Diagnose/analyze social problems, injustices, and policy gaps	1	2	3	4	5
9	Develop a political strategy (e.g., set goals, map stakeholders, identify barriers, etc.)	1	2	3	4	5

Interactional skills						
10	Build a coalition/alliance	1	2	3	4	5
11	Build personal power	1	2	3	4	5
12	Use rhetorical strategies	1	2	3	4	5
13	Advocate a position	1	2	3	4	5
14	Negotiate conflicts	1	2	3	4	5

Value-clarifying skills						
15	Identify the values grounding a policy	1	2	3	4	5
16	Engage in decision-making processes based on the ethical standards of social work	1	2	3	4	5
17	Consider the disadvantages and benefits of a policy	1	2	3	4	5

[Source: Schwartz-Tayri et al., 2021. Based on: Jansson, 2018]

10 VOLUNTARY POLITICAL PARTICIPATION

The following questions focus on your non-work-related, voluntary political participation as a citizen.

10.1 News Consumption

On a typical day, about how much time do you spend watching, reading or listening to news about politics and current affairs? Please give your answer in hours and minutes.

- Drop-down menu hours 0-23
- Drop-down menu minutes 0-59

[Source: ESS, 2020, question A1]

10.2 Voting

Some people do not vote nowadays, for one reason or another. Did you vote in the last election at the...

		Yes	No	Do not recall	Not eligible to vote
1	national level?				
2	state level?				
3	local level?				

[Source: adapted from ESS, 2020, question B13]

10.3 Voluntary Political Participation

There are different ways of trying to improve policies in [country] or help prevent things from going wrong. During the last 12 months, have you done any of the following? Have you...

		Yes	No
1	contacted a politician, government or local government official?		
2	donated to or participated in a political party or pressure group?		
3	worn or displayed a campaign badge/sticker?		
4	signed a petition?		
5	taken part in a public demonstration?		
6	boycotted certain products?		
7	posted or shared anything about politics online, for example on blogs, via email or on social media?		
8	volunteered for a not-for-profit or charitable organization?		

[Source: ESS, 2020, questions B15-B22]

11 SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

11.1 Degree 1

What are your educational qualifications?
(You can select more than one option)

- I'm currently still a student.
- Diploma of "Höhere Fachschule" (in Switzerland only)
- Bachelor (university or university of applied sciences)
- Master (university or university of applied sciences)
- PhD
- Habilitation

[Source: developed for this study]

11.2 Degree 2

In what discipline(s) did you obtain this/them?
(e.g. social work, education, political science)

- Open Text Field

[Source: developed for this study]

11.3 Age

Please indicate your age.

- Open Number Field

[Source: developed for this study]

11.4 Gender

How do you define your gender identity?

- Open Text Field

[Source: developed for this study]

11.5 Caregiving Obligations 1

Are you the primary caregiver of any children under 18 years of age or dependent adults?

- Yes
- No

[Source: developed for this study]

11.6 Caregiving Obligations 2. Filter. Show if Caregiving Obligations 1 = “yes”

How many children under 18 and/or dependent adults do you care for?

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- More than 6

11.7 Discrimination 1

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to answer
- I don't know

[Source: ESS, 2020, question C18]

11.8 Discrimination 2. Filter. Show if Discrimination 1 = “yes”

By which forms of discrimination are you affected?

- Open Text Field

[Source: developed for this study]

11.9 Last Question

This is the last question. Do you wish to share anything else about the topics covered in the survey?

- Open Text Field

[Source: developed for this study]

12 LAST PAGE

Thank you for taking part in the study. All your responses have been saved. You can close the browser window now. Please do not hesitate to reach out if you have any questions. Best regards,

Prof. Dr. Miriam Burzlauff, Tobias Kindler (MSW), and Dr. Talia Meital Schwartz-Tayri

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